

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No. B444
Date: 01 May 2009
Take Off: 13:11:41Z
Landing: 18:22:23Z
Flight Time 5h 10m 42s

Campaign: MEVEX Maritime (Dusk) Flight 6
Operating Area: Ocean, E of Oman

POB	Position	Name	Institute	Logs y/n
1	Captain	Alan Roberts	Directflight	
2	Co-pilot	Luc Lathouwers	Directflight	
3	CCM	Gaynor Ottaway	Directflight	
4	Mission Scientist	Dave Kindred	Met Office	
5	Flight Manager	Jim Crawford	FAAM	
6	Core Chem / AVAPS	Doug Anderson	FAAM	
7	Cloud Physics	Martyn Pickering	Met Office	
8	ARIES	Stuart Rogers	Met Office	
9	Wet Neph / CVI / IIR	Martin Glew	Met Office	
10	MARSS	James Bowles	Met Office	
11	Cameras	Joss Kent	Met Office	
12	Mini-LIDAR	Dave Pollard	Met Office	
13				
14				
15				
16				
17				
18				
19				

Missing Log Sheet	Reason
Brief	Sortie brief yet to be added
De-brief	Sortie De-brief yet to be created by ???
Mission Scientist 2	Mission Scientist 1 log not passed to FAAM for inclusion
Core Chemistry / TDLAS	no In Flight log except in cases of instrument problems
PSAP log	No log as PSAP pump/filter info included on Flight Summary page
CVI	No log passed to FAAM yet
IIR	No IIR log is provided for the Flight Folder

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	31 Dec 2009	Doug Anderson	Initial version missing the above noted logs
r1			

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

The following avi format video recordings should be available at the BADC in core_processed/faam-video :

faam-video-dfc_faam_20090501_r0_b444_131643_1hz.avi
 faam-video-dfc_faam_20090501_r0_b444_132645_1hz.avi
 faam-video-dfc_faam_20090501_r0_b444_142921_1hz.avi
 faam-video-dfc_faam_20090501_r0_b444_152921_1hz.avi
 faam-video-dfc_faam_20090501_r0_b444_153021_1hz.avi
 faam-video-dfc_faam_20090501_r0_b444_163358_1hz.avi
 faam-video-dfc_faam_20090501_r0_b444_173358_1hz.avi

faam-video-rfc_faam_20090501_r0_b444_131623_1hz.avi
 faam-video-rfc_faam_20090501_r0_b444_132634_1hz.avi
 faam-video-rfc_faam_20090501_r0_b444_142634_1hz.avi
 faam-video-rfc_faam_20090501_r0_b444_142744_1hz.avi
 faam-video-rfc_faam_20090501_r0_b444_143000_1hz.avi
 faam-video-rfc_faam_20090501_r0_b444_153028_1hz.avi
 faam-video-rfc_faam_20090501_r0_b444_163447_1hz.avi

faam-video-ffc_faam_20090501_r0_b444_131611_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ffc_faam_20090501_r0_b444_132630_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ffc_faam_20090501_r0_b444_142630_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ffc_faam_20090501_r0_b444_142737_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ffc_faam_20090501_r0_b444_142957_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ffc_faam_20090501_r0_b444_153025_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ffc_faam_20090501_r0_b444_163441_1hz.avi

faam-video-ufc_faam_20090501_r0_b444_131638_25hz.avi
 faam-video-ufc_faam_20090501_r0_b444_132638_25hz.avi
 faam-video-ufc_faam_20090501_r0_b444_142926_25hz.avi
 faam-video-ufc_faam_20090501_r0_b444_153016_25hz.avi
 faam-video-ufc_faam_20090501_r0_b444_163402_25hz.avi

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B444
 Date: 01 May 2009
 Project: MEVEX
 Location: Ocean east of muscat

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
130057		Start-Up	0.24 kft	267	
130615		ASP	0.23 kft	265	open
131141		T/O	3.0 kft	078	Muscat
132125		cpc	14.9 kft	084	on
132916	135305	Profile 1	17.0 - 0.19 kft	088	50ft qnh 1007.4 (F79)
134112		!	5.9 kft	090	cvi rack pcasp locked up
134313		P1	4.2 kft	090	interrupt
134505		P1	4.2 kft	257	resumed
135406		heimann	0.71 kft	286	cal 11
135632	140311	Run 1.1	1.1 - 1.2 kft	349	1000ft
135948		!	1.2 kft	345	overhead f79
140457	141200	Run 1.2	1.2 kft	183	
140843		!	1.2 kft	155	overhead f79
141312		heimann	1.2 kft	305	cal 11
141347	142201	Run 1.3	1.2 - 1.1 kft	354	
141619		!	1.2 kft	339	overhead f79
142318	143211	Run 1.4	1.2 kft	155	
142936		!	1.1 kft	209	overhead f79
143427	143934	Run 1.5	1.2 kft	036	
143609		!	1.2 kft	050	overhead f79
144112	144820	Run 1.6	1.2 kft	213	
144139		heimann	1.2 kft	219	cal 12
144153		cpc	1.2 kft	219	off
144522		!	1.2 kft	188	overhead f79
144834	145034	Profile 2	1.2 - 3.1 kft	219	
145035	145530	Run 2.1	3.1 - 3.2 kft	049	
145221		!	3.1 kft	027	overhead f79
145656	150552	Run 2.2	3.1 - 3.2 kft	188	
145713		heimann	3.2 kft	213	cal 12
150112		!	3.2 kft	197	overhead f79
150736	151022	Profile 3	3.2 - 1.1 kft	077	qnh 1010
152534	153413	Run 3.1	1.1 kft	199	
152613		heimann	1.1 kft	238	cal 12
153101		!	1.1 kft	192	overhead f79
153553	154049	Run 3.2	1.1 kft	032	
153757		!	1.1 kft	336	overhead f79
154212	155350	Run 3.3	1.1 kft	191	
154241		heimann	1.1 kft	225	cal 12
154647		!	1.1 kft	196	overhead f79
155634	160429	Run 3.4	1.1 kft	322	
160049		!	1.1 kft	327	abeam f79
160558	161240	Run 3.5	1.1 kft	167	
160633		heimann	1.1 kft	186	cal 12
160937		!	1.1 kft	156	overhead f79
161403	162055	Run 3.6	1.1 kft	333	
161722		!	1.1 kft	320	overhead f79
162224	162901	Run 3.7	1.1 kft	167	
162550		!	1.1 kft	156	overhead f79
163014	163703	Run 3.8	1.1 kft	308	
163048		heimann	1.1 kft	006	cal 12
163406		!	1.1 kft	338	overhead f79
163812	164401	Run 3.9	1.1 kft	131	
164036	164122	!	1.1 kft	157	overhead f79
164407	164613	Profile 4	1.1 - 3.0 kft	154	
164614	165158	Run 4.1	3.0 - 3.1 kft	339	
164651		heimann	3.1 kft	340	cal 12
164750	164846	!	3.1 kft	354	overhead f79
165410	170207	Run 4.2	3.1 kft	178	
165618		!	3.1 kft	161	overhead f79
170207	170420	Profile 5	3.1 - 1.1 kft	163	

170420	171224	Run 5.1	1.1 kft	353
170459		heimann	1.1 kft	001 cal 12
170936		!	1.1 kft	336 overhead f79
171335	171735	Run 5.2	1.1 kft	128
171640		!	1.1 kft	158 overhead f79
171736	173659	Profile 6	1.1 - 22.0 kft	175
174134		Sonde 1	22.0 kft	232
174314	175410	transit	22.0 - 21.0 kft	262
175410	182421	descent into muscat	21.0 - 0.17 kft	266
182223		land		
182439		ASP	0.17 kft	177 closed

B444 10:56:26-18:27:01

GLNG_PARA0581, GLAT_PARA0580

NEVEX
WHISKEY SUNSET

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.444** Date **1-5-09** Name **JRK** Page **1** of **8**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
1305					Start Taxi. (Stand 24) no PIRETTE CO ₂
1311					} 1/10 MOCAT 2/8 Ci, otherwise NIL CLOUD.
1313					
					THICK HAZE / Aerosol PASSING 3000'
131820	TRANSIT	10.0kft	088°	25° 26' N 88° 41' E	210/25 KT.
	T/Q	shows			low level hydrolysis near surface then near 2000' above 900 mb (~3000ft)
132115					Above main. BL top at 14000' with isothermal & strong hydrolysis (confirmed with Heph ↓ rapid fall 60' → 10m ⁻¹)
					(EXCELLENT BL TOP/LID). (2 on LID).
1329#6	Start PI	FL 170	090°		(1000'/min) Start PI towards ship in operation. 4/8 Ci (+ contrails) above
1333	BL Top	13500'			Sharp hydrolysis / Temp inversion (CO ₂ Heph, LID confirms):
1337		9200			Now into haze/aerosol top (visually)
1340					PCASP locked up on CNI rack
134313	PI	Interrupt PI at 4000'			Turning ↓ SHIP POS [23° 49.51' N, 160° 16.07' W]
134505	Resume PI ↓				Comms contact with ship; now auto S'y heading [in regard to ship]
					changed to 500'/min descent rate. 265/12 KT.
134833	PI ↓	2200'	242°		288°/814'. QNH = 1007.4 mb
					Visually q. hazy here
135305	END PI	50'			END PI (V. strong hydrolysis 20' change & inversion < 500ft).
					Repositioned TO START 1 st low approaching SHIP AT 1000'. FROM IN (ie. towards

1354 → CAMSERS Now WORKING (LONG WAVE ISS KENT LENGTH & MEDIUM WAVE DAVE LENGTH POLAR).

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B444** Date **1-5-09** Name **DK** Page **2** of **8**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
135632	START 21.1	1000'	009°		Approaching ship from 15nm.
135726		(1.11kft)			██████████
135803					██████████
135848					██████████
135948		██████████ O/H	SHIP How		(Slightly too far away). ONLY SHIP/TURT! Got at ^{nothing} on long wave / short wave. Spotter cameras' misbehaving, so no help in guiding into target.
140311	END 21.1	1000'			END 1 st run at 1000'. (~10 nm past ship) WIND CALM
140457	START 21.2	1000'	182°		Approaching from front of vessel.
140603					Range 10nm
140651					██████████ WIND 250° / 2kt. (variable)
140843		O/H	SHIP How		Top 1/3 of spotter, nothing seen on cameras (too close in)
1410					WIND 180° / 6kt. SEA STATE = 12. (LIGHT)
141200	END 21.2	1000'			Manceuvring to start 2 nd run
141347	START 1.3	1000'	005°	23 36 N 60 18 E	
141420					██████████
141538					Range 3nm. General following
141619		O/H	SHIP How		Westward top 1/3 of. Too close. Excellent view of wake as cutting across.
142201	END 21.3	1000'			045° / 2kt.
142318	START 21.4	1000'	171°		START 21.4 Dead astern in this run following
142427					Range 19nm (but only turning onto heading about few nm)

① X X
START RUN

② X X
START RUN

③ X
START RUN

W44 ✓

X VISUAL SIGHT 1425 X

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.444** Date **1-5-09** Name **DK** Page **3** of **8**

GMT	Run/Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
					██████████
1428		1000'	170°		5 miles.
142932		0/4	SHIP	down	Clearly saw wake LW saw wake, but no ship.
					} Getting double bounce on 'MASS'. Will switch off to (and) down every other run
143211	END R1.4	1000'			Will approach Bow of SHIP from HEAD ON THIS TIME.
143427	START R1.5	1000			██████████
143609		0/4	SHIP	Down	} Too far away from target. Full sequence of runs
14					
					More on camera. ██████████ , no ship.
143934	END 1.5	1000'			
144112	START R1.6	1000	218°		Start Heading W. (Approach from astern along wake).
144235					Range 10 nm.
14440				←	██████████
144522		0/4	SHIP		Capture MRENNING wave. ██████████
144820	END R1.6	1000'	(Climb)	210°	Low picked up also late with start END SEQUENCE OF RUNS AT 1000'
144834	to 3000' (P2)				
145035	END (P2)				1000' / m
	START 2.1	3000'			Range 7 nm (oblique run) " Saw and JOSE."

①
run to ship (from astern)
WAKE
✓ X

②
✓ X

③
✓ ✓

Mission Scientist's Log

LW = JVC
MW = DP.
-TMC

233 G)
601 OF

Flight No **B.444** Date 22K Name DK Page 4 of 8

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
			027°		████████████████████
145224		O/H SHIP	Now		O/H SHIP. SLIGHTLY CLOSER FOR LW CAN SEE
145513	END R2.1				Lumpy WX - Nothing seen
14565	START R2.2	3000'	222°		Run 2.2 Approaching ship (START R2.2)
					████████████████████
150112		O/H SHIP	Now		MW - Wake ✓, Ship seen ✓ LW - Wake ✓, Ship seen X
15055	END R2.2	3000'	221°		
			←	X	SHIP TURNING OFF TRACK N. ←
					████████████████████
150736	START P.3	3000' 2100'	077°		
151022	END P.3	1000'			Now at 1000' & Manoeuvring before starting slant runs stlly across hdg.
					Ship now on 220° hdg; changed winds & want to stay on 220° for next set of runs !! (INTO 20KT WIND)
START					OK, but A/C needs to reposition to new ship loc/hdg/;
BEFORE WAKE			SOME SIGNIFICANT MANOEVREING		WILL DO 4 CONSAT THIS SHIP HDG (220) (1000') HEADLAND (AL)
152534	START R2.1	1000'	222°		Appr. ship from slant (SLANT)
1528					Range 8 NM
153010					████████████████████
153301		O/H SHIP	Now		MW ✓ ship (Too far away) LW ✓ X
153413	END R2.1	1000'	192°		End slant run.

MW LW
7) V X

8) MW LW
Wake Ship Wake
✓ ✓ ✓

9) MW LW
Wake Ship Wake
✓ ✓ X

Mission Scientist's Log

Zeam
 LW - JSS
 MW - DMC P
 (Med Wave) 2) 26.5
 500 02.7

Flight No **B.444** Date **1-5-09** Name **JEK** Page **5** of **8**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
153553	START 23.2	1000'	054°		Approaching from SW this run (towards bow) (START)
153757		O/H Now			LW ✓ x ✓ MW ✓ ✓
154049	END 23.2	1000'			
154212	START 23.3	1000'	215°		Approaching stern. Wind 19S/20KT
154538		(1.1kft)			⇒ (START) TEMP 35.4 DP 9.2
154647		O/H Now			LW ✓ x MW ✓ ✓ (Sparrows below pickup)
1548				SHIP Now turning onto 360 HDG, 20KT.	(Need to be still closer)
155350	END 23.3	1000'	181°		END 23.3
155140					SHIP Now HDG 181, 20KT
155634	START 23.4	1000'	320°		START NEXT group of birds. SHIP ↑ 20KT
155756					Approaching wrong ship, so ↓ turning to get correct vessel
1600					[START] SHIP ↑
160049		O/H Now	(Abeam!)		LW x x MW x x
160200			336°		
160429	END 23.4	1000'			END
160558	START 23.5	1000' (1.1kft)	188°		HEIMAU CAL [START] SHIP ↑
160755			[157 (160910)]		[x/c]
160937		O/H Now			LW x MW ✓
161240	END 23.5	1000'			END R.

(10) LW ✓ x MW ✓
 (11) ✓ ✓ x
 (12) x x
 (13) MW ✓ LW x

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B-444** Date **1-5-09** Name **JRK** Page **6** of **8**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
161403	R3.6	1000'	009°		Approaching STEAM THIS RUN
161628			→		XXXXXXXXXX SHIP ↑
161722		O/H	SHIP		SW ✓
					MW ✓ stern ✓ Mid stern
162055	END R3.6				128° / (closer)
					N END WIND 125°/8KT Change in Lidar
					S END " 190°/30KT Views too. (More Aerosol)
162224	START R3.7	1000'	157°		LOST M wave (Dave P) Coors
					RANGE (C) ON M WAVE SHIP
162540		O/H SHIP			DIRECT HIT ATC. ↓
					LW / Med. wave
					Just came on in time for pass
162901	END R3.7	1000'	157°		(Wind up to 35KT, SSW here) (Lidar picking up)
163014	START R3.8	1000'	315°		Wind 205°/30kt. HIGH WAVE
1632					XXXXXXXXXX
163406		O/H SHIP			LW (Dave) X (Wave) ✓ (Too far away) MW (Dave) ✓ ✓
163703	END R3.8	1000'			WIND 135°/8KT [Less Aerosol]
163812	START R3.9	1000' (11kt)	175°		START LAST RUN FOR NOW THIS HEIGHT
					XXXXXXXXXX
164026		O/H SHIP			Phone/Wake

14
W MW
✓ ✓

15
YES
DIRECT HIT
✓ ✓

16
VV VV

17
SW
✓ X

164401 END R3.9 2climb to 3000'

164407 START R4

Mission Scientist's Log

→ 275

Flight No **B.444** Date **1-5-09** Name **JK** Page **7** of **8**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
16464	START R4.1	3000'	340°		155° / 12kt, START HEIGHT OK
164750		O/H SHIP			[REDACTED]
165158	END R4.1	3000'			waiter to pick up Mike or MW at this height
165410	START R4.2	3000'			SLASH ATTACK ON ^{THIS} NEXT ROW
165618		O/H SHIP			MW ship ✓ Turning into water.
16			178°		[REDACTED]
170000		3000'		→	Talking captain onto wake helo
170207	END R4.2	START P3			SHIP TURNING onto 276°, BUT BACK TO 360° 20kt FOR ANOTHER 5 MIN
170420	END P3 & START R5.1	1000'	353°		START FINAL ROW AT 1000'. (Approaching stern).
1706					SHIP NOW 360° Hdg [REDACTED]
170835			→		[REDACTED]
170936		O/H SHIP			MW (✓) LW X [REDACTED]
171224	END R5.1	1000'	350°		SHIP ASPECT TO STAY ON W BY HDG, 20kt FOR 1 FINAL PASS
171335	START R5.2	1000'	142°		[REDACTED]
171640	END R5.2	O/H SHIP			WIND 160° / 10kt water.
171735	END R5.2	1000'			END SHIP ROWS NOW
171736	START P8	1000'	180°		Change to FL 220 @ 1000' / mi

(18) LW MW (Joss) (Dave) W S W X X ✓ ✓

(19) ✓ ✓

XXX

(20) X ✓ ✓

(21) X ✓ ✓

B444-#mevexViRClog

```
[2009/05/01 01:52] *** Server connection lost
[2009/05/01 01:55] *** Nickname is already in use: FAAMOpsDetach
[2009/05/01 01:55] *** Server connection lost
[2009/05/01 01:56] *** FAAMOpsDetach (~vircuser@85.154.2.202) has joined #MEVEX
[2009/05/01 01:56] *** Mode change [+nt] on #MEVEX by photon.ge.phy.umist.ac.uk
*** Closed channel log for #MEVEX at 01/05/2009 04:24:08
*** Opened channel log for #mevex at 01/05/2009 14:29:11
[2009/05/01 14:29] *** FAAMOpsDetach (~vircuser@85.154.2.202) has joined #mevex
[2009/05/01 14:30] [FAAMOpsDetach] Re CPC - Jamie says no need to try running it in flight
[2009/05/01 14:32] [FAAMOpsDetach] Andy asks for a camera status update
[2009/05/01 14:42] <FAAM_flt_man> cpc never came out of 'warm up' and was switched off'
[2009/05/01 14:43] <FAAM_flt_man> cameras appear all good
[2009/05/01 14:43] <FAAM_flt_man> Peter's Wx received ok
[2009/05/01 14:44] <FAAM_flt_man> just completing first set of 6 at 1000, good data
[2009/05/01 14:49] [FAAMOpsDetach] Good stuff. We are all heading out for a noodle based dinner so
    will have to sign off VIRC but can talk via the Yahoo route
[2009/05/01 14:50] [FAAMOpsDetach] Peter is minding the back shop so I'll leave VIRC connected here
[2009/05/01 14:53] <FAAM_flt_man> OK - enjoy your noodles! I'll stay connected - ops ok
[2009/05/01 17:10] [FAAMOpsDetach] Noodles were good, and very plentiful
[2009/05/01 17:10] <FAAM_flt_man> oodles of noodles?
[2009/05/01 17:10] [FAAMOpsDetach] rather!
[2009/05/01 17:10] <FAAM_flt_man> not from a pot?
[2009/05/01 17:11] [FAAMOpsDetach] from Singapore apparently
[2009/05/01 17:12] [FAAMOpsDetach] how about on board, have you had your inflight feast?
[2009/05/01 17:14] <FAAM_flt_man> a feast so plentiful and sumptuous it was surely designed as a
    banquet for a king
[2009/05/01 17:14] [FAAMOpsDetach] and served on a silver salver no doubt
[2009/05/01 17:14] [FAAMOpsDetach] how long till your back?
[2009/05/01 17:15] <FAAM_flt_man> my back is about 28"
[2009/05/01 17:15] <FAAM_flt_man> beware the apostrophe abuse monster
[2009/05/01 17:17] [FAAMOpsDetach] I think I've got the measure of all that
[2009/05/01 17:18] <FAAM_flt_man> at 1000ft just starting our profile to sonde & return
[2009/05/01 17:20] [FAAMOpsDetach] 30 minutes for cash
[2009/05/01 17:21] [FAAMOpsDetach] pass the word, no cars booked for tomorrow (Hertz shut today) so
    we'll book it for Sunday
[2009/05/01 17:23] <FAAM_flt_man> 18:04 Z eta, can you confirm Peter knows
[2009/05/01 17:28] <FAAM_flt_man> message passed on
[2009/05/01 17:32] [FAAMOpsDetach] Peter fully informed
[2009/05/01 17:34] [FAAMOpsDetach] Andy is coming out to do camera calcs
[2009/05/01 17:42] <FAAM_flt_man> sonde good gozome transit
[2009/05/01 17:44] [FAAMOpsDetach] fandabidosie
[2009/05/01 17:47] [FAAMOpsDetach] The chappie from the National Survey is coming in tonight and
    wants to collect the videos for 27th (b439) and 30th. I thought he had
    already taken the B439 copy, do you know if this is the case?
[2009/05/01 17:49] <FAAM_flt_man> I'm sure he has had b439 - I guess I could write another?
[2009/05/01 17:53] [FAAMOpsDetach] i think he is getting confused about the day he collects the cds
    rather than the flight dates
[2009/05/01 17:53] [FAAMOpsDetach] another copy would be the safest bet though, just to keep him
    happy
[2009/05/01 17:55] <FAAM_flt_man> OK, shouldn't take too long, probably better than implying he is
    careless
[2009/05/01 18:01] [FAAMOpsDetach] yes, definitely
[2009/05/01 18:02] [FAAMOpsDetach] has it been a successful flight?
[2009/05/01 18:06] <FAAM_flt_man> moderate many near passes of wake or boat but few dead hits.
    generally satisfactory. The boat was being awkward by changing course without
    notice
[2009/05/01 18:07] [FAAMOpsDetach] Combat Metman at the helm maybe....
[2009/05/01 18:10] [FAAMOpsDetach] any instrument problems?
[2009/05/01 18:19] [FAAMOpsDetach] MoOps signing off
*** Closed channel log for #mevex at 01/05/2009 18:19:38
```

Cloud Physics Flight Log B444

Date: 01/05/09	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: 10:45:00	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	AUX1 Time: +0	AUX2 Time: +0
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DAU2 Disk space?

	PCASP SPP-200		CDP		PCASP		2DC		FFSSP		SID3	
Operated?												No
Pre-flight checks	Vref	7.5	Ref V (~3):	2	Vref (>7):	unkown	El#1 V (>1):	-1.2	Ref V:	3.5	Comms?	No
	Sample flow	1.15			Flow (~1):	0.64	El#32 V (>1):	-1.3				
	Sheath flow	14.29			Pressure:	1004						
					Temp (NDIT)	38						

GMT	Height	CDP		PCASP SPP-200		PCASP		2DC		Habit	FFSSP	SID3	Comments
		#/cc	MVD	#/cc	MVD	#/cc	Mean R	#/L	Max R				
13:19:00													Heater on old PCASP
13:25:00													Heaters on
13:29:14	FL170			80	0.3	30	0.07				4		Start Profile 1
13:30:11	FL160			80	0.3	50	0.08						
13:31:13	FL150			70	0.5	60	0.08						
13:32:10	FL140			70	0.5	60	0.08						
13:33:12	FL130	0.2	5	600	1	500	0.10						
13:34:20	FL120	0.3	10	700	1	600	0.10						
13:35:31	FL110	0.3	10	750	1	700	0.10						
13:36:38	FL100	0.3	10	800	1	720	0.10						
13:37:48	FL090	0.3	10	800	1	480	0.10				5		
13:39:03	FL080	0.2	10	600	1	500	0.10						
13:40:03	FL070	0.2	10	600	1	560	0.10						
13:41:06	FL060	0.1	7	600	1	570	0.10						
13:42:12	FL050	0.1	7	600	1	660	0.10						
13:43:19	FL040	0.2	7	700	1	620	0.10						Heaters off
13:47:30	FL030	0.2	7	800	1	830	0.10				6		
13:49:17	FL020	0.2	5	800	1	890	0.09						
13:50:58	FL010	0.2	5	1000	1	1000	0.09				7		
13:53:04	50'	0.2	5	900	1	1000	0.09						End of Profile
13:56:33	1000'												Start Run 1.1
13:57:00		0.2	7	900	1	850	0.09				8		
13:59:00		0.2	7	900	1	900	0.09				9		

GMT	Height	CDP		PCASP SPP-200		PCASP		2DC		Habit	FFSSP	SID3	Comments
		#/cc	MVD	#/cc	MVD	#/cc	Mean R	#/L	Max R				
14:01:00		0.2	10	900	1.5	900	0.09				10		
14:03:14													End of Run
14:05:06	1000'												Start Run 1.2
14:06:00		0.2	10	900	1.5	950	0.09						
14:08:00		0.2	10	900	1.5	900	0.09						
14:10:00		0.2	5	800	1.5	840	0.09				11		
14:11:59													End of Run
14:13:46	1000'												Start Run 1.3
14:14:00		0.2	5	900	1.5	900	0.09				12		
14:16:00		0.2	5	800	1.5	830	0.09				13		
14:18:00		0.2	5	850	1.5	830	0.09						
14:20:00		0.2	5	750	1.5	800	0.09				14		
14:22:06													End of Run
14:23:21	1000'												Start Run 1.4
14:24:00		0.2	5	700	1.5	740	0.09				15		
14:26:00		0.2	5	900	1.5	920	0.09						
14:28:00		0.2	5	800	1.5	750	0.09				16		
14:30:00		0.2	5	850	1.5	850	0.09						
14:32:12													End of Run 1.4
14:34:27	1000'												Start Run 1.5
14:35:00		0.2	5	900	1.5	50	0.09				17		
14:37:00		0.2	5	850	1.5	800	0.09				18		
14:39:00		0.2	5	850	1.5	800	0.09				19		
14:39:34													End of Run
14:41:13	1000'												Start Run 1.6
14:42:00		0.2	5	900	1.5	750	0.09						
14:44:00		0.2	5	850	1.5	850	0.09				20		
14:46:00		0.2	5	850	1.5	920	0.09						
14:48:24	1000'												End of Run & Start Profile 2
14:49:39	2000'	0.2	5	900	1.5	680	0.10				22		
14:50:35	3000'												End of Profile 2 & Start Run 2.1
14:51:00		0.15	7	900	1.5	800	0.09						
14:53:00		0.15	7	900	1.5	710	0.09						
14:55:00		0.15	6	900	1.5	750	0.09						
14:55:34													End of Run
14:57:04	3000'												Start Run 2.2

GMT	Height	CDP		PCASP SPP-200		PCASP		2DC		Habit	FFSSP	SID3	Comments
		#/cc	MVD	#/cc	MVD	#/cc	Mean R	#/L	Max R				
14:58:00		0.2	10	900	1.5	800	0.09				23		
15:00:00		0.2	7	900	1.5	750	0.09						
15:02:00		0.2	7	900	1.5	850	0.09				24		
15:04:00		0.2	7	950	1.5	800	0.09						
15:05:50													End of Run
15:07:46	3000'												Start Profile 3
15:09:08	2000'	0.3	7	950	1.5	950	0.09				25		
15:10:16	1000'	0.3	7	850	1.5	750	0.09	1					End of Profile
15:25:34	1000'												Start Run 3.1
15:26:00		0.2	7	900	1.5	900	0.09	1			28		
15:28:00		0.2	7	800	1.5	800	0.09	1					
15:30:00		0.3	7	750	1.5	710	0.10	1			29		
15:32:00		0.3	7	850	1.5	750	0.10	1					
15:34:13													
15:35:57	1000'												Start Run 3.2
15:36:00		0.3	7	800	1.5	750	0.09	1			30		
15:38:00		0.3	7	750	1.5	750	0.09	1			31		
15:40:00		0.3	7	750	1.5	730	0.09	1					
15:40:48													End of Run
15:42:11	1000'												Start Run 3.3
15:43:00		0.3	7	750	1.5	750	0.09	1			32		
15:45:00		0.3	7	800	1.5	750	0.09	1			33		
15:47:00		0.3	7	800	1.5	70	0.09	1					
15:53:50													End of Run
15:56:40	1000'												Start Run 3.4
15:57:00		0.3	7	850	1.5	730	0.09	1			36		
15:59:00		0.3	7	800	1.5	770	0.09	1					
16:01:00		0.3	7	800	1.5	780	0.09	1			37		
16:03:00		0.3	7	800	1.5	750	0.09	0.5					
16:04:28													End of Run
16:05:58	1000'												Start Run 3.5
16:06:00		0.3	7	800	1.5	760	0.09	1			38		
16:08:00		0.3	7	850	1.5	780	0.09	1			39		
16:10:00		0.3	7	800	1.5	750	0.09	0.5					
16:12:00		0.3	7	800	1.5	760	0.09	1					
16:12:45													End of Run

GMT	Height	CDP		PCASP SPP-200		PCASP		2DC		Habit	FFSSP	SID3	Comments
		#/cc	MVD	#/cc	MVD	#/cc	Mean R	#/L	Max R				
16:14:05	1000'												Start Run 3.6
16:15:00		0.3	7	850	1.5	750	0.09	0.5			40		
16:17:00		0.3	7	850	1.5	750	0.10				41		
16:19:00		0.3	7	800	1.5	800	0.09				42		
16:20:57													End of Run
16:22:31	1000'												Start Run 3.7
16:23:00		0.3	7	850	1.5	800	0.09				43		
16:25:00		0.4	7	800	1.5	740	0.09						
16:27:00		0.4	7	800	1.5	740	0.09				44		
16:29:03													End of Run
16:30:14	1000'												Start Run 3.8
16:31:00		0.3	7	800	1.5	750	0.09	1			45		
16:33:00		0.3	7	800	1.5	800	0.10	0.5					
16:35:00		0.3	7	800	1.5	750	0.10				46		
16:37:05													End of Run
16:38:12	1000'												Start Run 3.9
16:39:00		0.3	7	800	1.5	750	0.10				47		
16:41:00		0.3	7	800	1.5	770	0.10						
16:43:00		0.3	7	800	1.5	725	0.10				48		
16:44:05	1000'												End of Run & Start Profile
16:45:15	2000'	0.3	7	800	1.5	630	0.10						
16:46:15	3000'												End of Profile & Start Run 4.1
16:47:00		0.3	7	950	1.5	810	0.09				49		
16:49:00		0.3	7	1000	1.5	810	0.09						
16:51:00		0.3	7	900	1.5	740	0.10						
16:52:00													End of Run
16:55:30	3000'												Start Run 4.2
16:56:00		0.25	7	900	1.5	750	0.10				50		
16:58:00		0.25	7	1200	1.5	900	0.10				51		
17:00:00		0.25	7	1000	1.5	800	0.10						
17:01:58													End of Run
17:04:13	1000'												Start Run 5.1
17:05:00		0.2	7	800	1.5	850	0.10				52		
17:07:00		0.2	7	800	1.5	800	0.10				53		
17:09:00		0.3	7	800	1.5	800	0.10						
17:11:00		0.2	7	900	1.5	870	0.10				54		

GMT	Height	CDP		PCASP SPP-200		PCASP		2DC		Habit	FFSSP	SID3	Comments
		#/cc	MVD	#/cc	MVD	#/cc	Mean R	#/L	Max R				
17:12:27													End of Run
17:13:41	1000'												Start Run 5.2
17:14:00		0.3	7	850	1.5	840	0.09						
17:16:00		0.3	7	800	1.5	780	0.09						
17:17:37	1000'												End of Run & Start P6
17:18:27	FL020	0.3	7	850	1.5	720	0.09				55		
17:19:36	FL030	0.3	6	850	1.5	610	0.10						
17:20:27	FL040	0.3	7	900	1.5	660	0.09				56		
17:21:18	FL050	0.3	7	900	1.5	600	0.09						
17:22:20	FL060	0.3	7	900	1.5	500	0.10						
17:23:12	FL070	0.3	7	850	1.5	500	0.10						
17:24:13	FL080	0.3	7	850	1.5	450	0.10						
17:25:06	FL090	0.3	7	850	1.5	430	0.10						
17:26:10	FL100	0.3	7	850	1.5	400	0.10						
17:27:02	FL110	0.3	7	850	1.5	400	0.10						
17:28:01	FL120	0.2	7	800	1.5	250	0.10						
17:29:05	FL130	0.2	7	100	1.5	50	0.10						Heaters on Old PCASP
17:30:19	FL140	0.1	7	100	1	30	0.10				57		
17:30:53	FL150			100	0.5	35	0.08						
17:31:50	FL160			100	0.3	15	0.07						Heaters on
17:32:45	FL170			60	0.2	20	0.06						
17:33:36	FL180			50	0.2	25	0.07						
17:34:22	FL190			50	0.2	15	0.07						
17:35:13	FL200			50	0.2	25	0.07						
17:36:00	FL210			40	0.2	20	0.07						
17:36:59	FL220			40	0.2	25	0.07						End of Profile
18:01:00													Heaters off
18:04:00													Old PCASP heater off

Post flight

Instrument	Diagnostics		Brief report on instrument performance
PCASP (old)	Vref:	Unkown	Noisy when high and cold
	Flow:	0.7	
2DC	EI#1:	-1.2	
	EI#32:	-1.2	
PCASP SPP-200	Ref V:	7.6	
	Flow:	1.36	
CDP	Laser V:	3.84	
FFSSP	Ref V:	3.4	
SID 3	Laser V:	N/a	
Rack Equipment		1.0GB	Please note SEADAS disk space remaining.

BHKK
01 MAY 09

F79
23 2F.5N
060 02.7E.

Flight:

B444

KEY

 Not Fitted

 Fitted, Not Operated

 Duff Data

 Minor Problem

 OK

Thermometers

Cabin Temperature:
 Heimann:
 Deiced Temp:
 Non-deiced Temp:

Hygrometers

FWVS:
 Buck CR2:
 General Eastern:
 Johnson Williams:
 Nevzorov:
 Total Water Probe:

Cameras

Downward Facing:
 Forward Facing:
 Rearward Facing:
 Upward Facing:

Navigation + Aircraft

Cruciform GPS:
 GIN Applanix:
 INU Honeywell:
 Radar Altimeter:
 RVSM IAS:
 RVSM Static Pressure:
 XR5 GPS:

Misc Core

HORACE:
 AMTG:
 AVAPS:
 Cabin Pressure:
 Printer:
 S9 Static Pressure:
 Satcom C:
 Satcom H (VIRC):
 Turb Centre-Static:
 Turb Left Right:
 Turb Up-Down:
 Turb Horizontal Chk:
 Turb Vertical Chk:
 Weather Radar:
DLUs:
 DLU AERACK:
 DLU BBR Lower:
 DLU BBR Upper:
 DLU Core Chem:
 DLU Core Consoles:
 DLU Port Aft:
 DLU Port Fwd:
 DLU Stbd Fwd:

Radiometers

Lower:
 BBR (clear) Lower:
 BBR (IR) Lower:
 BBR (red) Lower:
Upper:
 BBR (clear) Upper:
 BBR (IR) Upper:
 BBR (red) Upper:
 ARIES:
 DEIMOS:
 IR Camera:
 JNO2 Lower:
 JNO2 Upper:
 JO1D Lower:
 JO1D Upper:
 MARSS:
 SHIMS Lower:
 SHIMS Upper:
 SWS:
 TAFTS:

Cloud Probes

2DC:
 2DP:
 FFSSP:
 PCASP:
 PCASP SPP-200:
 2DS:
 ADA:
 CAPS:
 CCN:
 CDP (fuselage):
 CDP (Canister):
 CIP 100 (PIP):
 CIP 25 (CIP):
 CPI:
 CVI (Inlet):
 CVI PCASP-X:
 CVI Ly-A Hygro:
 FSSP (UMan):
 SID1:
 SID2:
 SID3:

Aerosol

CPC 3025A:
 CPC 3786 H2O:
 Filters 47mm:
 Filters 90mm:
 Neph - Dry:
 Neph - Wet:
 PSAP:
 AMS:
 CPC (AMS):
 SMPS (AMS):
 CPC 3010A (CVI):
 INC:
 Mini-LIDAR:
 SP2:
 UHSAS:
 VACC:

Chemistry

CO Aerolaser 5002:
 NOx TE42C:
 Ozone TE49C:
 Ozone TE49:
 SO2 TE43C:
 TDLAS (NIR) CH4:
 TDLAS (NIR) CO2:
 FAGE:
 Formaldehyde:
 NOx FAAM:
 NOxy:
 ORAC:
 PAN:
 PERCA:
 Peroxide:
 PTRMS:
 TDLAS (1C):
 WAS Bags:
 WAS Bottles:
Misc Non-Core
 CASI/ATM:
 LIDAR (big):
 LTI:
 SAW Hygrometer:

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B444

Date: 01 May 2009

Instruments

cloud physics

SID3 not operated

old pcasp works ok below fl180, noisy above, channel 2 & higher ok

new pcasp no noise from SWS 28V (sws not operated) but still noisy data

CVI – pcasp ok, CPC dead

IIR – good

wet neph good

dry neph ok, blue channel zero suspect

Nezvorov; failed sensor, not operated

Chemistry – good data, ozone overheated early but recovered

AVAPS – one good sonde

MARSS – good data

SWS/SHIMS -not operated

ARIES – good data

Mini Lidar – good data “fantastic”

filters – not flown

FWVS – good data though some “wierdies”

SATCOM-H: mpds service good

GIN – serviceable

Aircraft

Satcom-H Calls

nil

Post Flight - Turb Probe Water Traps

1. Indicate Amount of Water: a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) ¼ full or more d) Ice present
2. Emptied by:
3. Dried by:

Pre-Flighter's Log

^ Clipboard power button

Date: 1/5/09

Flight No: B 444

Pre-Flighter: Phil Rosenberg

No.	✓ or x	Location	Action	Comments
1	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Hangar	Collect Dustbin, put on a/c	N/A
<u>Aircraft Cabin: Power-up</u>				
2	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Core Chemistry	Gases x 3 ON	operator
3	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Cabin	All Racks Checked	
4	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Fwd CorCon	All reqd CBs made	
5	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Aft CorCon	CBs made, PCs ON	
6	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	Optical Disk loaded	
7	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	Recording data	
8	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	DLU Status Checked	
9	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	HORACE Status Checked	
10	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Satcom H	Power LED ON	
11	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Nevzorov	Checked and OFF	NOT RUN
12	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	GPS	Checked	
13	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	INU	Align	N/A
14	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Cameras Pictures	Checked x 4 OK	
15	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Core Chemistry	Instruments Checked OK	operator
16	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Core Chemistry	CO Flows Checked OK	operator
17	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	FWVS	Set up & check on AUTO	operator
18	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Video x 2	Records okay, Rewind	N/A
19	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Delced Rosemount	Heater Checked then OFF	
20	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Heimann	Calibration Checked	
21	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	TWC	ON & Checked	
22	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	GE	Balance checked	
23	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	INU	Navigate then back to Align	N/A
	<input type="checkbox"/>			
	<input type="checkbox"/>			
	<input type="checkbox"/>			

No.	✓ or x	Location	Action	Comments
24	<input type="checkbox"/>	CNC	Butanol filled	
25	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Dry Neph	Power up & Zero Cal	operator
26	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Miss. Sci Laptop	Checked Onboard	In cockpit
27	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	CGPS	CBs and PC ON	N/A
28	<input type="checkbox"/>			
<u>External Checks</u>				
29	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Turb Probe	Clean if reqd, Photo taken	
30	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	JW	Cleaned & Checked	
31	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	DI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
32	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	NDI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
33	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Nevzorov	Cleaned/windings checked	
34	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	GE	Cleaned & Checked	
35	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Lower BBRs	Domes cleaned/checked	
36	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Camera Windows	Cleaned	
37	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Heimann	Lens checked OK	
38	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	TWC Cover	Fitted if required	
39	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	All other covers	Removed	
40	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Dustbin	Returned to hangar	
41	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Pre-flight Bag	Returned to hold	** Check no butanol**
42	<input type="checkbox"/>	Tools	Check ALL in Toolkit	
43	<input type="checkbox"/>	Tools	Avalon informed	
<u>Avalon Checks</u>				
44	<input type="checkbox"/>	Upper BBRs Checked & Cleaned		Signed
45	<input type="checkbox"/>	ICEX applied		
46	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Turb Probe - Traps emptied, detail contents -		a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) 1/4 full or more
47	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Turb Probe - Traps dried and resealed		

ARIES flight log

Flight: B444 page 1 of 2

Date: 01/MAY/09 Operator(s): S. Rogers Res: 1 Gain A: 2 B: 2

Loc./Notes: Mexico: Ship wake

Scans: either "[IGMs][co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Comments
~1200	—						Power on OK. Switching off during pre-flight as it's cloudy but around here.
~1310	Takes off						
13 24 15	↑ FL170	cal	CH	0	81	42	CH cal window 40C mirror 16C
13 27 51	FL170	NadirZen	NZ	0	81	41	Nadir Zenith 30sec. macro - abject de to descent
13 54 50	1000*	N3min	N	0	81	42	Nadir 3min
14 03	1000	ZBmin	Z	0	81	45	Z1min - Flocking CBS
14 05 15	1000	N3min	N	0	81	45	Nadir 3min
14 10 58	"	120x1	Z	0	81	46	Zenith
14 12 49	"	N3min	N	0	81	46	Nadir 3min (start in time) horizon
14 20 23	"	120x1	Z	0	81	47	Zenith
14 21 31	"	N3min	N	0	81	47	Nadir 3min
14 31 25	"	120x1	Z	0	81	49	Zenith
14 32 22	"	N3min	N	0	81	49	Nadir 3min
14 41 19	"	N3min	N	0	81	49	Nadir 3min
14 48 31	↑ "	cal	CH	0	81	49	CH cal
14 50 16	↑ 3000'	N3min	N	0	81	49	Nadir 3min
15 01 54	"	120x1	Z	0	81	48	CH Zenith
15 02 58	"	cal	CH	0	81	48	CH cal
15 10 22	1000	N3min	N	0	81	47	Nadir Lots of fanning around waiting for a ship to get its act together
15 33 06	"	120x1	Z	0	81	49	Zenith
15 34 25	"	N3min	N	0	81	49	Nadir Shrewk! It's hot back here!
15 40 04	"	120x1	Z	0	81	49	Zenith
15 40 58	"	N3min	N	0	81	50	Nadir
15 50 51	"	120x1	Z	0	81	50	Zenith
15 53 33	"	N3min	N	0	81	50	Nadir
16 03 30	"	120x1	Z	0	81	51	Zenith
16 04 35	"	cal	CH	0	81	50	CH cal
16 06 15	"	N3min	N	0	81	50	Nadir
16 11 55	"	120x1	Z	0	81	50	Zenith
16 12 53	"	cal	CH	0	81	50	CH cal
16 14 10	"	N3min	N	0	81	50	Nadir

Microwave Radiometers FLIGHT LOG		Date	010509	Flight	B444	log pages
Operator(s)	J Bowles		Campaign	MEVEX		
Departure	Muscat		Arrival	Muscat		

System start

MARSS

Visual pod inspection						Y
Close 3 SSP circuit breakers						•
Close all MARSS circuit breakers						•
FERA on					at time	11:38
Temperature controller initial temps	Ch16	40.1°C	Ch 17	40.1°C	Ch18	39.9°C
Temperature controller set points		54°C		58°C	-20	40°C
MARSS CPU on					at time	
Initial target temperatures	Hot	320	Cold	315		
Target heating						•
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***						•
Scanning on (LMD box)					at time	
Scan indication	Monitor			•	Visual	•

Deimos

Close all Deimos circuit breakers						
Turn on Deimos CPU						
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***						
Start Deimos Software					at time	
Initial target temperatures	Hot		Cold			
Target heating						
Scan indication	Monitor				Visual	
Weather	Cloud		Precip			
	Surface		Pressure			
	Other					

System functionality check

(after initial system warmup, approx 1 hour)

PC to DRS Time error	$t_{PC}=t_{DRS} +$	0	at time	13:16:00	
Brightness temps 'sensible'					•
Target temps	MARSS:	Hot	344.5	Cold	308.6
	Deimos:	Hot		Cold	
Channel gains 'sensible'	Ch1 A (-)	Ch3 A (-)	Ch1 B (-)	Ch3 B (-)	
	Ch16 (40-44)	Ch17 (45-49)	Ch18 (40-44)	Ch19 (40-44)	Ch20 (44-48)
	37.45	31.63	39.74	39.5	37.9

Power changeover

Headset on before start		•
Listen to engine start sequence	4, 3, 2, 1.	•
LMD off (3 switches, bottom to top)		•
Exit Deimos Software (x)		
POWER CHANGEOVER		
LMD on (3 switches, top to bottom)	then pushbutton	•
Restart Deimos Software		
System running again		at time

Flight #	B	Date		Operator(s)		log page	2	of	2
Time	Run id	Alt/FL	Remarks				Sys		
	pre		Only test scan for preflight. Scan proper after takeoff. Phew what a scorcher!						
13:13	Trans		Scanning						
			Plan: Scan for runs and stop for turn arounds to keep things cool.						
14:01:24	R1.1	1000	Stop, too early, couple min after ship.						
14:05:07	R1.2	"	Scanning						
14:12:10	R1.2	"	Stop scanning						
14:14:10	R1.3	"	Scanning						
14:19:50	R1.3		Stop, some double bounce creeping in						
14:23:30	R1.4		Scanning						
14:25 ish	R1.4		Double bounce on this run						
14:32:09	R1.4	1000	Stopped.						
			New Plan, scan every other run to cool and avoid double bounce.						
14:41:30	R1.6	1000	Scanning						
14:44:16	R1.6		Still double bounce!						
14:48:41			Stop.						
14:57:20	R2.2	3000	scanning						
14:59:45			Double bounce cut in						
15:04:20	R2.2	3000	stop						
			Next plan, miss two runs to cool. Back to 1000ft						
15:25:40	R3.1	1000	scanning						
15:34:25	R3.1	1000	Stop. GOOD RUN.						
15:56:45	R3.4	1000	Scanning						
16:03:18	R3.4	1000	Double bounce start						
16:04:40	R3.4	1000	Stop, MOST OF RUN CLEAR.						
16:22:50	R3.7	1000	scanning						
16:29:10	R3.7	1000	Stop. GOOD RUN,						
16:38:30	R3.9	1000	scanning						
16:42:00	R3.9	1000	Stop, double bounce, abandon run, cool down.						
16:45:30			Restart Radmon software, data coming in very fast despite not scanning						
16:47			Restart MARSS software. Hot count data seems very fast, but other radmon windows ok						
17:04:30	R5.1	1000	Scanning						
17:12:40	R5.1	1000	Stop. GOOD RUN						
17:13:50	R5.2	1000	Start						
17:17:40	Eor 5.2	1000	GOOD RUN, leave scanning for prof up.						
17:20:00	P6		Double bounce, stop scan						
17:36:50	P6		scanning						
18:26:30			Stop scan.						
18:29:30			MARSS time 18:29:40						

Wet Nephelometer Log

Flight No **B444**

Date 01/05/2009

Operator's name Martin Glew

Page .1..... of2.

GMT	Run	Height	Sample flow	Dry neph RH	Wet neph RH	Temp ramp	T _{water}	Remarks
1235								Operating as double neph. Both nephs zeroed. Pre-flight w/d ratios close to 1 at 8.5 l/m. A little reduction in w/d ratio at 12.7 l/m. Perhaps more at 15 but interrupted for security. Ratio now centered on 0.9 with red more depressed on 0.8. Full flow red ratio 0.45, green 0.65, blue 0.75
1259								full flow for take off
13:36:00								In transit looks like a slightly bad zero on dry neph blue, others not so bad
13:56:32	R1.1	1000 ft	20	15.8	15.3			Full flow this run. W/D ratios: blue 0.45, green 0.34, red 0.22
14:04:57	R1.2	1000 ft	11.1	16.5	16.1			Trying for W/D ratios of 1. Achieved: blue 1, green 1, red 0.9. Absolute values 80-100 m-1
14:10:57								W/D ratios now deviating from 1
14:13:47	R1.3	1000 ft	18.5	17.8	16.5			Ratios: blue 0.68, green 0.56, red 0.46. Ratios stable down run
14:23:18	R1.4	1000 ft	8.0	15.5	15.3			Ratios: blue 0.95, green 0.85, red 0.85
14:34:27	R1.5	1000 ft	max	20.0	17.4			Max wet neph flow. Ratios: blue 0.5, green 0.35, red 0.22
14:41:12	R1.6	1000 ft	5	20.7	16.5			Ratios: blue 0.9, green 0.9, red 0.85
14:50:35	R2.1	3000 ft	19.8	17.8	15.1			Maximum flow rate that is not default max. Ratios: Blue 0.68, green 0.56, red 0.46
14:56:56	R2.2	3000 ft	12.0	15.5	14.0			A guess at a high non-impacting rate. Ratios: blue 0.88, green 0.8, red 0.75
15:25:34	R3.1	1000 ft	max	18.7	16.7			Max flow rate. Ratios: blue 0.43, green 0.30, red 0.18
15:35:53	R3.2	1000 ft	19	30.5	24.4			Ratios: blue 0.6 , green 0.53, red 0.43
15:42:12	R3.3	1000 ft	17.0	24.6	20.5			Ratios: blue 0.65, green 0.56, red 0.48
								??? ratios always seem higher after flow rate change, then drift down a little???
								???Effect independent of sign of flow change. Might be correlated with turns though but???
15:56:34	R3.4	1000 ft	15.0	33.1	25.2			Ratios: blue 0.65, green 0.58, red 0.50

ALS450 LIDAR FLIGHT LOG

FLIGHT NUMBER: 13444
 DATE: 1/5/7
 Campaign: MEVET

OPERATOR: POLLARD
 WATER FILL: 15.0h ~ 10mh
 WATER EMPTY:
 Ct: 2,110,473 / 2,449,554
 Cw: 2,110,473 / 2,449,554

Run No:	Altitude	Start Time	Stop Time	Int. Time	Head Temp	Water Temp	Notes
		15:01			40	39.7	initial water temp!
Trens	74ft	13:16		10s			
		13:28					Good return from top of MBL ~ 1000m below
					39	37.5	
R's 1		Still using 10s int time and resolving structure in MBL					
		MBL dipping down after sunset			39	37.5	@ 15:15
			1800				End
			1830		31	37.8	Shut down

Flight B444 17:45:42

Heading 264 deg Speed 302 knots Height 22.0kft Press 427mb

Lat 23°48.0'N Long 60°0.0'E Wind 13 ms-1/ 284 deg

Temp -16.33C Dewpoint -31.58C

From start to now

Current values			
++++ PRESSURE HEIGHT	22.02	Kft	<input checked="" type="radio"/> All
REFRACTIVITY	131.7	Munits	<input type="radio"/>

Flight B444 17:45:25

Heading 264 deg Speed 302 knots Height 22.0kft Press 427mb

Lat 23°48.0'N Long 60°6.0'E Wind 14 ms-1/ 284 deg

Temp -16.35C Dewpoint -31.5C

From start to now

Current values
----- PRESSURE HEIGHT
REFRACTMITY

22.02 Kft
131.73 Munits

All

Flight B444 17:44:55

Heading 265 deg Speed 299 knots Height 22.0kft Press 427mb

Lat 23°48.0'N Long 60°6.0'E Wind 13 ms-1/ 283 deg

Temp -16.33C Dewpoint -31.38C

From start to now

Current values		
GIN LONGITUDE	60.16	deg (+ve E)
GIN LATITUDE	23.88	deg (+ve N)

Flight B444 17:44:03

Heading 263 deg Speed 294 knots Height 22.0kft Press 427mb

Lat 23°48.0'N Long 60°12.0'E Wind 13 ms-1/ 280 deg

Temp -16.2C Dewpoint -32.12C

From start to now

Current values			
	PRESSURE HEIGHT	22.02	Kft
+++++	NEPH BLUE SP	-0.9	m-1
.....	NEPH GREEN SP	-0.9	m-1
+++++	NEPH RED SP	-0.8	m-1

Flight B444 17:43:46

Heading 262 deg Speed 291 knots Height 22.0kft Press 427mb

Lat 23°48.0'N Long 60°12.0'E Wind 13 ms-1/ 279 deg

Temp -16.15C Dewpoint -31.81C

From start to now

	Current values			
	PRESSURE HEIGHT	22.02	Kft	<input checked="" type="radio"/> All
----	NEPH BLUE SP	-0.9	m-1	<input type="radio"/>
----	NEPH GREEN SP	-0.9	m-1	<input type="radio"/>
----	NEPH RED SP	-0.55	m-1	<input type="radio"/>

Flight B444 17:43:10

Heading 263 deg Speed 288 knots Height 22.0kft Press 427mb

Lat 23°48.0'N Long 60°18.0'E Wind 13 ms-1/ 281 deg

Temp -16.26C Dewpoint -31.9C

From 17:03:17 to now

	Current values		
	STATIC PRESSURE	427.24	mb
++++	DEICED TRUE AIR TEMP	-16.26	deg C
++++	DEW POINT	-31.91	deg C

Flight B444 14:07:29

Heading 170 deg Speed 212 knots Height 1.1kft Press 971mb

Lat 23°48.0'N Long 60°12.0'E Wind 1 ms-1/ 233 deg

Temp 35.25C Dewpoint 2.16C

From start to now

Current values				
-----	PRESSURE HEIGHT	1.15	Kft	<input checked="" type="radio"/> All
-----	NEPH BLUE SP	76.35	m-1	<input type="radio"/>
-----	NEPH GREEN SP	71.45	m-1	<input type="radio"/>
-----	NEPH RED SP	65.58	m-1	<input type="radio"/>

Flight B444 14:07:20

Heading 171 deg Speed 213 knots Height 1.1kft Press 971mb

Lat 23°48.0'N Long 60°12.0'E Wind 1 ms-1/ 230 deg

Temp 35.19C Dewpoint 2.24C

From 12:45:56 to now

	Current values		
-----	STATIC PRESSURE	971.63	mb
+++++	DEICED TRUE AIR TEMP	35.2	deg C
+++++	DEW POINT	2.25	deg C

Flight B444 13:28:10

Heading 89 deg Speed 294 knots Height 17.0kft Press 527mb

Lat 23°42.0'N Long 59°36.0'E Wind 11 ms-1/ 234 deg

Temp -4.01C Dewpoint -37.29C

From 12:45:56 to now

	Current values		
	STATIC PRESSURE	527.02	mb
++++	DEICED TRUE AIR TEMP	-4.01	deg C
-----	DEW POINT	-37.29	deg C

Flight B444 13:30:26

Heading 86 deg Speed 292 knots Height 15.8kft Press 552mb

Lat 23°42.0'N Long 59°48.0'E Wind 9 ms-1/ 255 deg

Temp -3.06C Dewpoint -27.83C

From start to now

	Current values		
	PRESSURE HEIGHT	15.85	Kft
(.....)	NEPH BLUE SP	4.15	m-1
(.....)	NEPH GREEN SP	7	m-1
(.....)	NEPH RED SP	3.87	m-1